

An Interdigital Planar Energy Harvesting/Storage Device Based On an Ionic Solid–Gel Polymer

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ABSTRACT:

The generation of efficient self-powered energy harvesting/storage technologies is a milestone demand to the field of the Internet of Things. In this work, an interdigital planar all-in-one thermally chargeable supercapacitor (IPTS) was successfully produced by merging energy harvesting and storage technologies. The smart device was produced through a photolithography process, combining carbon nanotubes as an electrode material with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) doped with H₃PO₄ as a solid–gel polyelectrolyte. The ionic conductivity of PVA doped with H₃PO₄ was tuned by changing the amount of H₃PO₄ within the PVA matrix, unveiling an optimum ratio of PVA/H₃PO₄ of 1:1 (m/m). The power generation performance of the IPTS was evaluated. The device reached a Soret coefficient of 2.35 mV K⁻¹, which is one order of magnitude higher than those of thermoelectric materials (few hundreds of μV K⁻¹). Moreover, it reached a voltage generation output of up to 45 mV for ΔT = 20 K. Concerning energy storage features, the device worked as an electric double-layer capacitor, affording an energy density of 1.05 mW h cm⁻³ at a power density of 1.21 W cm⁻³. The tailored interdigital configuration, high flexibility, and energy efficiency of the IPTS, combined with a cost-effective production process that offers the possibility of scale-up, open unique horizons in the field of flexible electronics.

KEYWORDS: thermally chargeable supercapacitor, thermoelectric device, carbon nanotubes, polyelectrolyte, energy materials

1. Introduction

The demand for electronic wearables able to monitor physiological signals, body movement, and geolocation, among other applications, has stimulated the quest for flexible devices with an autonomous power source, the so-called self-powered systems.^{1,2} Energy harvesting (EH) devices appear as a promising solution to power Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, namely, EH systems able to convert heat into electricity, the so-called thermoelectric converters.³⁻⁵ The conversion of heat into electricity is being applied for over 50 years, namely, using thermoelectric devices composed of narrow band gap semiconductors. The operation mechanism of these systems is based on thermally-driven electron diffusion, defined as the Seebeck effect.⁶⁻⁹ However, the low output voltages ($\sim 200 \mu\text{V K}^{-1}$), high fabrication costs, and need for several thermoelectric pillars to reach useful outputs are major constraints to the implementation of thermoelectric technology.¹⁰⁻¹² Recently, two novel classes of thermal EH devices based on the ion transport mechanism emerged—thermogalvanic cells and thermodiffusion-based devices.¹³⁻¹⁶ These devices exhibit distinct underlying operation mechanisms: a thermogalvanic mechanism and ionic thermodiffusion. Thermogalvanic cells are based on redox reactions that occur at the interfaces between the electrodes and the electrolyte. One of the major drawbacks is the fact that most thermogalvanic cells use liquid electrolytes. Nevertheless, very recently, an ionic gelatin was used as an electrolyte, leading to an impressive thermopower of 17 mV K^{-1} near room temperature.¹⁷ One of the advantages of thermogalvanic cells is that they can be continuously producing energy, acting as DC generators. EH devices based on ionic thermodiffusion are also composed of two electrodes and an electrolyte. It is the working principle that is different from that of thermogalvanic cells, consisting in the diffusion of ions within the electrolyte when a temperature gradient (ΔT) is applied between both electrodes, lacking the occurrence of redox reactions at the electrode/electrolyte interfaces. In this case, the electromotive force (EMF) arises from the opposite movement of the electrolyte ions mainly by the Soret effect.¹³ Thermodiffusion-based devices work in capacitive mode, i.e., after the EMF is established, they can only be discharged when an external load is applied.¹⁴ Under a steady-state condition, the thermopower (S) due to ion thermodiffusion is expressed by $S = (\alpha_+ - \alpha_-)(k_B/e)$,¹⁸ where α is the Soret effect of the cation (+) or anion (-), k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and e is the electron charge. Thus, when ΔT is applied across a sample, a thermally induced voltage, ΔV , on a steady state, is generated,

and the thermopower S_i is achieved from the linear slope of ΔT vs ΔV relation. The output is measured by the energy density (E_D), which depends on both the capacitance (C) and ionic Seebeck coefficient (S_i), and is expressed by $E_D = \frac{1}{2} C(S_i \Delta T)^2$. Since these types of devices work as capacitive systems, a major asset is their ability to operate as hybrid technologies, i.e., they can simultaneously work as energy harvesting and energy storage systems, thus disposing the need for batteries. Despite these potentialities, this field of research is still at an embryonic stage, with only scarce examples being reported as proof-of-concept. For instance, in 2016, Zhao and co-authors¹⁴ used a polymeric electrolyte based on liquid poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) treated with NaOH to charge a carbon nanotube (CNT)-based supercapacitor under a ΔT , obtaining an ionic Seebeck coefficient of 11.1 mV K^{-1} . However, liquid electrolytes require bulky packaging to prevent leakage and complicated fabrication steps and present fast degradation and toxicity, being difficult to be applied on flexible devices.^{15,19} Moreover, they present undesirable low electrical conductivity¹⁴ when compared to solid-state electrolytes.²⁰ In the same year, Kim and co-authors¹³ reported a thermally chargeable supercapacitor using a polystyrene sulfonic acid (PSSH) film both as a solid electrolyte and voltage generator and polyaniline (PANI)-coated graphene and CNT films as positive and negative electrodes, respectively, which sandwiched the PSSH electrolyte. The device contained mobile hydrogen cations and rather immobile PSS anions, reaching a thermovoltage of 8 mV K^{-1} at 70% relative humidity (RH) and exhibiting a good electrical conductivity of 9 S m^{-1} . Nevertheless, the cost and the possibility of working under limited RH conditions were pointed out as the main limitations of the device. Recently, Kundu and Fisher²¹ produced a flexible thermally chargeable supercapacitor through the use of the thermogalvanic gel electrolyte PVA/ $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6/\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (PFC) combined with cost-effective carbon cloth electrodes. The device could store energy from intermittent temperature gradients and subsequently power on-demand portable electronic devices. The energy storage properties were assigned to a pseudocapacitive charge storage mechanism involving the occurrence of redox reactions at the surface and near the surface of the active electrode materials, which limited the power density and cycling lifetime of the device when compared to electric double-layer capacitors (EDLCs).²² The use of polyelectrolytes, such as PVA, has the advantage of endowing thermopower stability to the device upon relative humidity variation, as reported in ref 19. Another exciting approach was reported by Kim and co-authors¹⁵ that produced a thermally chargeable supercapacitor device lacking a polyelectrolyte and in a planar configuration. The device was based on laser-

reduced graphene oxide films intercalated by sulfate ions and did not require any liquid-phase electrolyte, achieving $\sim 9 \text{ mV K}^{-1}$ per module.

Despite this progress, interdigital planar structures remain almost unexplored as well as the use of scalable manufacturing processes, which are of prime importance for industrial applications. The combination of supercapacitive properties and the thermoelectric Soret effect upon a small ΔT on a single device can be the future to supply low-power electronic devices. Moreover, a long walk road needs to be taken concerning the material optimization and structural design in order to enhance the efficiency of the device and accelerate the scale-up fabrication process.

In the present work, we propose a novel and advanced architecture device to be used as a self-powered system, consisting of an interdigital planar hybrid merging energy harvesting and storage properties an interdigital planar thermal ionic micro-supercapacitor (IPTS). Although this configuration is well known in the supercapacitor research field, to the best of our knowledge, it has never been tested as a thermodiffusion EH system. Our approach combines the use of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) as an electrode material with PVA doped with phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) as an ionic solid-gel polymer. The simplicity and cost-effective production process, allied with high-performance features and scalability, make this device sustainable for low-grade applications.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, PVA- H_3PO_4 was selected as an electrolyte due to its safety since it is a solid-gel electrolyte and presents thermopower stability without RH dependence. Additionally, it is well known that solid-gel electrolytes are attractive due to their easy handling, low internal corrosion, lightness, shape versatility, and manufacturing simplicity when compared to liquid electrolytes that require bulky packaging to prevent leakage.^{14,15,19}

In [Figure 1a](#)) is presented the variation of the ionic conductivity of PVA doped with H_3PO_4 upon the increase in the H_3PO_4 loading, ranging from 15 to 85 wt %, obtained by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Figure 1. a) Ionic conductivity of the PVA- H_3PO_4 polymer gel electrolyte for different weight percentages of H_3PO_4 . (b) SEM image of MWCNTs deposited on the PET substrate (20,000 \times magnification). The inset of b) is the high-magnification micrograph of the MWCNTs (200,000 \times magnification).

For H_3PO_4 loadings smaller than 75 wt %, a linear behavior of the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte is observed, with a slope of $1.15 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ per wt % of H_3PO_4 , reaching 0.082 mS cm^{-1} for 75 wt %. This behavior unveils that H_3PO_4 is effectively doping the PVA insulator with ionic charges. For 85 wt % of H_3PO_4 within the polymer, the conductivity remains similar to the value obtained for 75 wt %, showing that there is a doping limit of PVA polymer with this acid. Although the PVA doped with 75 wt % of H_3PO_4 exhibits the highest ionic conductivity, for concentrations above 50 wt %, technical drawbacks appeared during the device fabrication, namely, a drastic increase in the curing process time combined with a performance degradation of the IPTS device over time, probably arising from the high acidic character of the corresponding electrolyte. Thus, 50 wt % was selected as the optimal concentration since it combines the highest value of ionic conductivity of the electrolyte ($7.85 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$) with good physical integrity.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was conducted to evaluate the quality of the produced interdigital electrodes. The SEM images of the MWCNTs deposited on the polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substrate, presented in Figure 1b), and the initial powder (inset Figure 1b) reveal the typical tubular structure of the MWCNTs²³ and their random orientation throughout the substrate.

The IPTS prototype studied herein was produced in a planar geometry (i.e., with the electrodes side-by-side in the same plane as the electrolyte) and with the electrodes in an interdigital configuration, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Fabrication process of the IPTS prototype: (I) design of the electrode architecture (interdigital finger design) using photolithographic processes; (II) electrode fabrication by filling the created pattern with MWCNT-based ink; and (III) coating with the PVA-H₃PO₄ solid-gel electrolyte.

The fabrication process can be divided into three steps: (I) design of the electrode pattern on the PET substrate using photolithographic processes (described in detail in the [Experimental Section](#)); (II) production of the patterned electrodes through deposition of the MWCNT-based ink on the created design; and (III) coating of both MWCNT-based electrodes with a thin film of the solid-gel electrolyte (PVA-H₃PO₄).

The electrochemical performance of the device was evaluated by EIS, cyclic voltammetry (CV), and galvanostatic charge/discharge experiments (GCD) at room temperature (RT) in a two-electrode cell configuration to unveil its energy storage properties. The EIS technique, which measures the impedance of the device (expressed in Ω) as a function of the frequency (Nyquist plot), allows unveiling the type of energy storage mechanism and determining the equivalent series resistance (R_{ESR}). As depicted in [Figure 3a](#)), the Nyquist plot (frequency range of 20 Hz to 3 MHz) shows that the electrode behavior strongly depends on the frequency. From the extrapolation of the linear range in the low-frequency region,²⁴ an R_{ESR} of 376.17 Ω is obtained at RT, which is similar to the internal resistance extracted at 1 kHz. Furthermore, it is possible to observe an inconspicuous arc in the high-frequency region that shows that the electric resistance of the CNT nanomaterial is low, which is in good agreement with the literature and typical of EDLCs.²⁵ CV analysis was performed to determine the specific storage capacitance of the device. [Figure 3b](#)) exhibits the i - V cycles at different scan rates from 1 to 100 mV s^{-1} . A non-faradaic electrostatic charge storage mechanism was detected due to the quasi-rectangular curve shape of the cyclic voltammograms, which is typical of EDLCs.²⁶ This means that during charging/discharging of the device, adsorption/desorption of electrolyte ions into/from the surface of the MWCNT-based electrodes occurs. Moreover, it is well known that through the analysis of the i - V curves, the areal, C_A (expressed in F cm^{-2}), volumetric, C_V (expressed in F cm^{-3}), or gravimetric C_g (expressed in F kg^{-1}) specific capacitance values can be determined, where C_A is more related

to the specification of the supercapacitor device, whereas C_V and C_g are more related to the specifications of the electrode materials. The specific capacitance can be determined by the following expression:²⁷

$$C_X = \frac{1}{2 X_t \nu \Delta V} \int_{-V}^{+V} i(V) dV \quad (1)$$

where C_X can be C_A , C_V , or C_g and X_t is the active surface area of the device, total volume, or total mass of the electrode active nanomaterials, respectively; ν is the potential scan rate expressed in $V s^{-1}$, ΔV is the potential window expressed in V, and i is the current intensity expressed in A.

Figure 3. a) Nyquist plot (Z'' vs Z') of the IPTS obtained from EIS measurements performed at RT in a frequency range of 20 Hz to 3 MHz. b) CV cycles of the IPTS device measured at different scan rates (1, 5, 10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 $mV s^{-1}$) in the potential window between -1.0 and 1.0 V. c) Variation of the volumetric specific capacitance of the IPTS as a function of the potential scan rate. d) Galvanostatic charge/discharge curve of the IPTS device ($i = 0.5$ mA); the inset of d) shows in more detail the IR_{Drop} . e) Charge and discharge curves at different current densities: 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 $mA g^{-1}$. f) Cycling stability test of the IPTS during 6000 charge/discharge cycles; the inset of (f) shows all 6000 i - V cycles.

A maximum volumetric capacitance of $C_V = 1.70 \text{ F cm}^{-3}$ ($C_A = 1.36 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ or $C_g = 802.36 \text{ F kg}^{-1}$) is achieved at a scan rate of 1 mV s^{-1} . In Figure 3c) is depicted the variation of the volumetric specific capacitance as a function of the scan rate. It is possible to observe that the specific capacitance decreases upon the increase in the scan rate tending to stabilization at high scan rates. This variation is related to the shorter time for the formation of the electric double-layer of the EDLC at higher scan rates, while at lower scan rates the electrolyte ions have more time to accommodate in the pores of the electrodes.²⁷ The specific capacitance of the IPTS at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} is $C_V = 1.18 \text{ F cm}^{-3}$ ($C_A = 0.95 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$), which is in good agreement with the values found in the literature for interdigital supercapacitors.^{14,28,29} For instance, Zhao and co-authors¹⁴ reported areal specific capacitance values of 0.95 and 0.48 mF cm^{-2} for thick and thin MWCNTbased electrodes, respectively, at a similar scan rate (10 mV s^{-1}) using PEO–NaOH as a liquid electrolyte. The dynamics of the as-produced IPTS was also determined through the characteristic capacitor relaxation time given by $\tau = CR_{\text{ESR}}$ (with τ , C , and R_{ESR} expressed in s , F , and Ω , respectively),²⁴ leading to an IPTS operation frequency ($f = 1/2\pi\tau$) of 0.29 Hz .

Figure 3d) shows the results of the GCD characterization of the device, which was performed to determine its operating voltage. In this analysis, a 0.5 mA current intensity was applied for 60 s (charge) to ensure the voltage saturation at the end of the charging step (under open circuit). Through this figure, it is possible to observe that the device reaches an operating voltage V_0 of 2.11 V (maximum voltage value). After switching off the load charge current, it is possible to observe an IR_{Drop} that corresponds to the voltage jump immediately before and just after switching off the current.^{24,27} An IR_{Drop} of 0.187 V was achieved (inset of Figure 3d), revealing the low internal resistance of the device, thus reinforcing the EIS results. Furthermore, the characteristic capacitive behavior of the device was evaluated by performing charge and discharge tests at different current densities ($2, 4, 6, 8,$ and 10 mA g^{-1}), as shown in Figure 3e). The almost symmetric linear shape of the charge and discharge curves confirms the EDLC-type behavior of the IPTS, which is in accordance with the i - V results. In Figure 3f) is presented the cycling stability test of the IPTS during 6000 charge/discharge cycles. The device exhibits a capacitance retention of 96.4% after 6000 cycles, confirming its excellent cyclability.

The inset of Figure 3f) shows that the i - V curves maintain the shape of the initial i - V cycle over all the 6000 charge/discharge cycles.

The energy density (E_x) and power density (P_x) values of the IPTS, which are considered the key parameters to define the energy storage performance of any device, were determined by considering the operating voltage, the specific capacitance, and the dimensions of the device. For EDLCs, the E_x and the P_x can be calculated from eqs 2 and 3, respectively:^{27,30,31}

$$E_X = \frac{1}{2} C_X V_0^2 \frac{1}{3600} \quad (2)$$

and

$$P_X = \frac{V_0^2}{4X_t R_{ESR}} \quad (3)$$

where E_X can be E_A (areal), E_V (volumetric), or E_g (gravimetric), expressed in $W h cm^{-2}$, $W h cm^{-3}$, or $W h kg^{-1}$, respectively, and P_X can be P_A (areal), P_V (volumetric), or P_g (gravimetric), expressed in $W cm^{-2}$, $W cm^{-3}$, or $W kg^{-3}$, respectively.

Using the abovementioned equations, a volumetric energy density E_V of $1.05 mW h cm^{-3}$ ($0.84 \mu W h cm^{-2}$ or $0.50 W h kg^{-1}$) and a volumetric power density P_V of $1.21 W cm^{-3}$ ($0.97 mW cm^{-2}$ or $573.25 W kg^{-1}$) were obtained for the device produced in this work. The achieved outputs are promising and comparable to the results reported in the literature.³² For instance, Li and co-authors³² reported a stretchable microsupercapacitor based on polyaniline-coated MWCNT electrodes and a poly(methyl methacrylate)-propylene carbonate- $LiClO_4$ gel electrolyte and obtained a P_A of $0.07 mW cm^{-2}$ and an E_A of $0.004 mW h cm^{-2}$.

Concerning energy harvesting, the thermovoltage values under open circuit (V_{OC}) caused by different temperature gradients ΔT ranging from 4 to 20 K are presented in Figure 4a. The voltage values were measured for 7500 s ($\sim 2 h$), and the maximum values of the $V(t)$ curves as a function of the corresponding ΔT are represented in the graph of Figure 4b.

Figure 4. a) Thermovoltage under open circuit measured over time for different ΔT (4, 8, 12, 16, and 20 K). b) ΔV maximum values as a function of ΔT . The insets of b) show the infrared thermal image of the device when a temperature gradient is applied (bottom right) and the linearization of the characteristic time of diffusion as a function of ΔT (top left).

As can be observed from Figure 4a), the V_{OC} vs t curves present a behavior typical of a cumulative function, which is characteristic of the charging process on a supercapacitor through the imposed thermal gradient. For $\Delta T = 20$ K, a maximum thermovoltage of ~ 45 mV is obtained. Notice that the only constraint is the heat reservoir temperature that should not surpass 85 °C to avoid PVA degradation.^{33,34}

The plot of ΔV_{max} as a function of ΔT demonstrates that the thermovoltage varies linearly with ΔT , leading to an ionic Seebeck coefficient (S_i) of 2.35 mV K⁻¹ determined by

$$\Delta V_{max, thermal} = |S_i| \Delta T \quad (4)$$

This result is at least one order of magnitude higher than the values reported for the most common thermoelectric materials used for RT applications, e.g., Bi_2Te_3 , which presents an absolute Seebeck coefficient of ~ 0.2 mV K⁻¹.³⁵ Moreover, it is 1.67 times higher than the value reported for a thermoelectrochemical cell based on a ferricyanide/ferrocyanide liquid electrolyte (1.4 mV K⁻¹)³⁶ and 3.9 times higher than that of commercially available supercapacitors that present a thermal-induced voltage of ~ 0.6 mV K⁻¹ in a temperature range of 0 – 65 °C.³⁷ When comparing with the use of PVA as an electrolyte, our result is up to two times higher than that obtained for a device based on PVA doped with ferro/ ferricyanide redox couples (-1.21 mV K⁻¹).²¹ Additionally, the Seebeck coefficient achieved in the present work is comparable to those obtained for electrolytes composed of a cobalt complex (1.9 mV K⁻¹)³⁸ and triiodides (2.0 mV K⁻¹).³⁹ The time evolution of ΔV is governed by the Soret ion diffusion through the interdigital structure, given by the onedimensional expression $\Delta V(t) = \Delta V_0 + A \left(1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} e^{-t/\theta} \right)$, where θ is the characteristic time of diffusion and $A = \Delta V_\infty - \Delta V_0$.⁴⁰ From the fitting of the experimental ΔV vs t curves for each ΔT , the time of diffusion θ exhibits a linear ΔT dependence with a value of 131 s K⁻¹ (see the inset of Figure 4b). Since the ion diffusion coefficient is given by $D = \pi \theta^2 l^2$, with l being the distance between the electrodes (0.1 cm; see Figure S1 in the Supporting Information), an estimated D of 7.74×10^{-10} m² s K⁻¹ is obtained.⁴¹

In Figure 5a) is presented the charge/discharge cycle achieved for the as-produced device, and in Figure 5b) is proposed the electrochemical operating mechanism of the IPTS, which can be explained in four steps: (1) initial state; (2) charge; (3) storage; and (4) discharge state. A similar explanation is given by Zhao and co-authors¹⁴ for the nature of the observed effects.

When $\Delta T = 0$ K (state 1), the electrolyte ions are randomly distributed in the electrolyte medium: this corresponds to the initial state of the thermal charging behavior. Immediately after applying a temperature gradient (from state 1 to state 2), the migration of the electrolyte cations (from a H_3PO_4 ion donor) toward the cold electrode occurs due to the Soret effect.

Figure 5. a) Voltage curve of the IPTS device as a function of time when a temperature gradient $\Delta T = 10$ K is applied; the inset of (a) shows the $V(t)$ curves for different R_{load} values. b) Schematic explanation of the electrochemical operating mechanism of the IPTS highlighting the electrolyte ion motion during the thermal charging, where (1) is the initial state, (2) is the charged state, (3) is the storage state, and (4) is the discharged state; the “-” symbol corresponds to the electrolyte anions and the “+” symbol to the electrolyte cations.

Therefore, an electromotive force is generated of around 19 mV for $\Delta T = 10$ K. This electromotive force arises from the fast diffusion of the electrolyte cations (H^+) toward the electrode on the cold side, while less mobile PO_4^{3-} anions remain at the hot side, as previously reported by other authors.^{13,42} Due to this mobility of the ions, an increase in the voltage is observed, which almost stabilizes after ~ 1 h 23 min. The charging process (state 2) occurs when an R_{load} is applied between the electrodes in order to allow the electron movement in the outer electronic circuit from one electrode to the other and their subsequent accumulation at the electrode to compensate the electromotive force generated by the electrolyte ions motion: this corresponds to the charged state. Afterward, when ΔT and R_{load} are removed, the energy storage process occurs (state 3) by retaining the charge on the electrodes due to the open circuit. Then, to power supply an electronic system, the IPTS is connected to a device and a disequilibrium of the

electrolyte ions starts to appear, which corresponds to the discharged state (state 4), thus generating an electric current on the outer circuit. Notice that during the discharge process, the unloading of the micro-supercapacitor occurs, causing the random migration of the cations (H^+) inside the electrolyte medium.

The energy storage or scavenged energy achieved from the thermal gradient was determined through eq 2, considering the retained voltage of the device for $\Delta T = 10$ K (Figure 5a). An E_D of ~ 118 nWh cm^{-2} was achieved, which corresponds to a charge on the electrodes, Q_{ch} , of 128 mC cm^{-2} determined through the following equation:⁴³

$$Q_{ch} = C(S_i \Delta T) \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the electronic outputs achieved by the IPTS prototype proposed herein demonstrate its potentialities as a promising solution to integrate energy conversion and storage on a single device that can simultaneously use the wasted heat from the environment, convert it into electrical energy, and store it. Finally, from Figure 5a), the periodic time of full working operation of the IPTS to get maximum charge for each ΔT is $\sim 10,000$ s.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Herein, an all-in-one ionic thermoelectric supercapacitor device that simultaneously combines energy storage and thermoelectric properties was produced with an interdigital planar configuration. The solid-gel H_3PO_4 -doped PVA electrolyte combined with MWCNTs as an electrode material opened the possibility of achieving a high Seebeck coefficient value (~ 2.35 mV K^{-1}) and of simultaneously using the applied temperature gradient to charge a supercapacitor due to the temperature-induced movement of the electrolyte ions between the hot and cold electrodes.

Regarding the energy storage performance, the IPTS reached an energy density of 1.05 mW h cm^{-3} at a power density of 1.21 W cm^{-3} . Concerning the thermoelectric performance, the device achieved an ionic Seebeck coefficient of 2.35 mV K^{-1} and could reach ~ 45 mV in open circuit for $\Delta T = 20$ K.

The as-produced IPTS device is susceptible to small thermal gradients, offering promising prospects to be used, for example, to recover the heat wasted from the human body. The ability to be produced in a planar configuration provides several advantages when compared to sandwich-type 3D structures, namely, concerning the fabrication process, since printing techniques can be used, thus being compatible with scale-up and implementation at an industrial level. Moreover, the IPTS can be integrated in mobile and wireless electronics and connected to sensors that require discontinuous monitorization. The IPTS' major advantage

when compared to thermoelectric devices is its high output voltage (2.35 mV K⁻¹ vs value in the order of $\mu\text{V K}^{-1}$ for inorganic thermoelectric materials). Thus, the ionic thermoelectric device reported in this work constitutes a promising advance for the next-generation of self-powered devices.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

4.1. Materials. Commercial MWCNTs (NC7000™) were used as an electrode material and purchased from Nanocyl SA, with an average diameter of 9.5 μm and an average length of 1.5 μm .⁴⁴ A stable aqueous dispersion of MWCNTs with 10 mg mL⁻¹ concentration was prepared using sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (Sigma-Aldrich) as a surfactant. PVA (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) doped with orthophosphoric acid (85%, analytical grade, Fisher Chemical) was used as a solid-gel electrolyte. The electrolyte was prepared by solubilization of PVA in an H₃PO₄ aqueous solution, in 1:1 weight ratio, at 90 °C under continuous stirring; water promotes the dissociation of H₃PO₄ into H⁺/H₂PO₄⁻.¹⁹

4.2. Device Fabrication. A 2D interdigital planar all-solid-state device (1.52 cm²) was fabricated using two photolithography processes and a PET substrate that served as a support for the construction of the final device.⁴² Each photolithographic process was carried out in several stages, presented in [Figure 1](#): (1) PET substrate cleaning, (2) spreading of the photoresist by a spin-coating technique followed by a soft bake process, (3) mask alignment, (4) photoresist development, (5) deposition of the chosen material, and finally (6) a lift-off process using acetone. The AZ6632 2.4 μm photoresist was used and purchased from Clariant AG. The corresponding developer for the photoresist was AZ 726 MIF. A full optimization of the photoresist concerning exposure time and development was carried out before the device fabrication. Accordingly, the spin-coating was performed using 4000 rpm for 1 min; the soft-bake was performed at 110 °C for 50 s followed by UV exposure for 12 s using the Karl Suss MJB-3 equipment and photoresist development for 50 s in a pure developer. Concerning the device fabrication, first, Au electrical contact patterns were produced through the first photolithography process and then deposited by a sputtering technique. Afterward, a second photolithography process was performed with the aim of producing the interdigitated electrodes with four stripes interconnected between them. After both photolithography processes, the produced patterns were filled with the dispersion of MWCNTs and dried in air. Finally, the patterns of the device were coated with 400 μL of the PVA-H₃PO₄ solid-gel electrolyte

(covered area of 7.5 cm²). A real image of the IPTS device can be seen in [Figure 2](#). Also, in [Figure S2](#) in the Supporting Information are shown the dimensions of the device and a 3D representative image of the construction of the device.

4.3. Characterization. The morphology of the MWCNTs deposited on the PET substrate was analyzed by SEM using Philips-FEI/Quanta 400 equipment (CEMUP-Porto, Portugal). The electrochemical performance of the IPTS prototype was evaluated at RT by EIS, CV, and GCD experiments on a standard two-electrode cell configuration. EIS was performed in a frequency range of 20 Hz to 3 MHz with a $V_{\text{BIAS}} = 1$ V to determine the equivalent series resistance of the device. CV measurements were performed at scan rates of 1, 5, 10, 20, 25, 50, 75, and 100 mV s⁻¹ in a range of ± 1.0 V and GCD measurements were conducted at $i = 0.5$ mA, both using a Keithley Instruments apparatus (model 2400). Charge and discharge tests were performed at different current densities of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 mA g⁻¹. The thermoelectric device performance was measured using a commercial tungsten microprobe system, where the prototype was placed between two temperature-controlled Peltier's stages (TEC112706) and a temperature gradient was applied and controlled by a TC-08 Thermocouple datalogger (Pico Technology) using k-type thermocouples. Herein, the ΔV between two electrodes was measured using a nanovoltmeter from HP Instruments (model 34420A). ΔT values between 4 and 20 K were used, and the thermopower was obtained from the linear slope that is defined as $\alpha = \Delta V/\Delta T$.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was financially supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)/MEC and FEDER under Program PT2020 through the projects PTDC/CTM-NAN/ 5414/2014, PTDC/CTM-TEX/31271/2017, UIDB/04968/ 2020, UIDB/50006/2020, and NORTE-01-0145-FEDER022096 from NECL. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 863307 (ref. H2020FETOPEN-2018-2019-2020-01). A.L.P. thanks FCT for the grant under the project PTDC/CTM-NAN/5414/2014. R.S.C. thanks for the grant funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 863307 (H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2019-202001). C.P. thanks FCT for the FCT Investigator contract IF/ 01080/2015. The authors also acknowledge the CEMUPMNTec lab for the nanofabrication.

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